

Welcome to the 1st volume of the EU-HIP Newsletter!

Hello and welcome to the EU-HIP newsletter. As this is the first edition, we will kick-off with a short introduction to our project. Get to know what EU-HIP is doing and how it is contributing to the work of DG HERA. After you catch the basics we will continue with the most recent updates coming from the General Assembly and Symposium held in Zagreb and HERA 2023 Conference. For the end we have prepared some interesting reads and connections to projects which are connected to our work.

Ready? Let's dive into it!

What is HERA?

The Health Emergency Preparedness and Response (HERA) Authority's mission is to prevent, detect, and rapidly respond to health emergencies. HERA, created in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic, will anticipate threats and potential health crises, through intelligence gathering and building the necessary response capacities. When an emergency hits, HERA will ensure the development, production and distribution of medicines, vaccines and other medical countermeasures – such as gloves and masks – that were often lacking during the first phase of the response to the COVID-19 pandemic. For intelligence gathering and threat assessment, HERA is currently developing a state-of-the-art IT system called ATHINA. Responsible authorities from Member States will connect to the platform and provide the data needed to safeguard the health of European citizens in case of any emergency.

Introducing: EU-HIP

Let's start with the full name of the project - EU-HIP stands for: EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform. Financed by the European Health and Digital Agency, it is a 30-month long project that aims to provide much needed support to Member States which are going to connect to ATHINA. The platform can only be fully operational if the Member States have national IT systems for intelligence gathering in place and if the systems are interoperable. Participating countries will, in a coordinated manner, strengthen existing IT systems or build new ones collaborating with other partners to achieve interoperability from the beginning. Moreover, there is focus on promoting data comparability and streamlining reporting of different systems. Points of interest cover the topics of medical countermeasures, antimicrobial resistance, pathogens with high pandemic potential as well as chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear threats.

General Assembly and Symposium in Zagreb

At the end of November, from 27th to 28th, we have gathered in the capital of Croatia, Zagreb to hold the annual General Assembly and EU-HIP Symposium. With more than 50 participants from 15 different EU countries attending in-person and additional guests joining online, we had the opportunity to meet, discuss and exchange experiences gathered during the first months of the project. As the hosting country, Croatia has prepared a Site Presentation where it layered down it's plan to strengthen it's national IT system. Representatives from HERA have joined the event with a presentation about the development of ATHINA with timelines and expected capabilities. A direct communication channel between our project consortium and DG HERA was established during this meeting and will potentiate a successful implementation of inputs provided by Member States to ATHINA as well as facilitate exchange of information and experiences in both ways.

In the past weeks we have put a lot of effort in the development and conduction of a landscape analysis. The aim of it is to get a general overview of types of data collected in different Member States, the sources used, interoperability standards implemented and of their potential availability. Preliminary results of the analysis have been shared in Zagreb with a notion that Croatia will be the first country within the consortium to undergo a more in-depth analysis executed by partners from Sciensano, Belgium. The results of the landscape analysis and specific country profiles will be developed in close future and will be shared with you, our readers, in one of the following volumes of this newsletter.

Annual HERA conference

The EU-HIP Project was represented at the 2023 HERA Conference in Brussels on December 5th 2023. A great interest in the project and the topic of health and preparedness data interoperability in Europe was expressed by the many conference participants that visited the stand of EU-HIP. The conference was a great opportunity to discuss synergies between the EU-HIP project and other European projects such as MOOD, EU-WISH, DURABLE, United4Surveillance and more.

**Connected
project:**

For every project it is crucial to connect with other projects in the same or related fields, with activities which are in-line or can complement it. The same goes for our consortium which would like to drive your attention to a project which is worth to get to know: DURABLE - Delivering a Unified Research Alliance of Biomedical and public health Laboratories against Epidemics.

DURABLE will coordinate a global collaboration, from pathogen detection, evolutionary analysis and threat characterisation, with the One Health approach, to data and information collection and sharing, for optimal threat response. DURABLE will develop and validate a roadmap for rapid deployment of key countermeasures, test the robustness of the network, and assess key aspects of its emergency mode when simulating or dealing with identified threats. Additionally, DURABLE will focus on long-term sustainability by focusing on capacity building, training the next generation of researchers and developing pandemic preparedness training modules for the network and beyond.

Read more about the project at durableproject.org

**HAPPY
HOLIDAYS**

FROM THE EU-HIP TEAM!